

BLAST LOAD EFFECTS ON LAMINATED COMPOSITE CIRCULAR CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

Carlos R. Plazaola

Jack R. Vinson

Department of Mechanical Engineering

University of Delaware

Newark, Delaware 19716

ABSTRACT

The dynamic response of laminated composite material circular cylindrical shells subjected to axially symmetric blast loads is investigated, including the effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia, using the Reissner-Naghdi shell theory. Separation of variables and the method of eigenfunction expansions are employed. First a free vibration analysis of the composite shells is performed, including the effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia, and the natural frequencies are determined. Then, the dynamic response to five types of blast loads are investigated. These include the half sine pulse, the stepped pulse, the triangular pulse, the stepped triangular pulse (typical of nuclear blasts), and the exponentially decaying pulse. Results are presented for several graphite/epoxy shells including unidirectional axial laminates, unidirectional circumferential laminates, various cross-ply laminates, as well as a steel isotropic shell for comparison purposes. The effects of shell wall thickness to mean radius (h/R) ratios are also shown, as well as the effect of transverse shear deformation.

The five types of blast loads are compared, and the most severe load is determined. Some general conclusions regarding the effects of the blast duration are given. Also, for each blast load type, the time and magnitude of the maximum deflection and maximum stress are clearly shown. Design implications are discussed. Although results are shown explicitly for the shells, materials, and loads outlined above, certain generalizations are clear for shells of other configurations, materials, boundary conditions, asymmetries, and differing lamination patterns.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the publication of Love's paper [1] in 1888 a great deal of research has been devoted to the study of the vibrational characteristics of shells of varied geometries. The circular cylindrical shell, having the simplest geometry, has been the subject of exhaustive study. However, with the development of advanced structural materials further research is necessary.

A very good review of the literature published until 1972 appears in the work of Leissa [2]. Vinson and Chou [3] and Vinson and Sierakowski [4] present a review of the literature published during the 1970s and early 1980s.

In the last decade the free and forced vibrations of isotropic and anisotropic layered shells have been studied by Chonan [5,7,8], Soedel [9], Sheinman and Greif [6], Alam and Asnani [10, 11, 12], Bhimaraddi [13], Lee [14], Chao and Chern [15], Sadasiva Rao [16], Greenberg and Stavsky [17], Hirano [18, 19], and Kayran [20-23]. A more detailed discussion of the above research is presented by Plazaola [24].

In the present work, the response of laminated composite material circular cylindrical shells subjected to blast loads is presented. The materials are assumed to be orthotropic, and linear elasticity theory is utilized. Since for unidirectional composite materials the properties are strongly directional, the effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia are also investigated. Several laminate configurations are considered. Five pulse shapes are studied, and the effects of the pulse duration are analyzed as well. The Reissner-Naghdi theory is used to carry out the analysis. For this study it is assumed that the pulse load acts on the shell structure uniformly over its outer or inner surface, thus, the loading is axisymmetric. The approach to solve the equations of motion is based on the methods of separation of variables and eigenfunction expansions.

2. ANALYSIS

The geometry of a laminated composite material circular cylindrical shell is shown in Figure 1. The positive directions of the coordinate axes (x, θ, z) are shown, as well as the positive directions of the displacement components. The radius of the middle surface of the shell is R , and the shell length is denoted by L .

Figure 1. Shell coordinates and displacement components.

The shell analysis used herein is based on the following hypotheses:

- Displacements are small compared to the shell thickness, and displacement gradients are small, such that linear strain-displacement relations may be used.
- The Kirchhoff hypotheses are applicable, except that the assumption that line elements normal to the middle surface before deformation remain normal after deformation is relaxed (transverse shear deformations exist).
- Love's First Approximation is valid.
- Each lamina is considered to behave macroscopically as a homogeneous, orthotropic, linearly elastic material.
- The bond between laminae is perfect.
- The shell is not subjected to gravitational, electric or magnetic fields.
- Material and air damping effects are not included.
- Thermal and hygrothermal effects are neglected.

The details of the derivations are found in Reference [24] and not included herein for brevity. The A, B and D stiffness matrix quantities are the standard ones given in all the texts including [3, 4].

Combining the equations of dynamic equilibrium, the kinematics and the constitutive equations, and considering the case of an axisymmetric load a set of partial differential equations are obtained, as usual, which represent the dynamic equilibrium in terms of displacements and rotations.

In this study, the shells considered do not involve stretching-shearing, twisting-stretching, bending-shearing and bending-twisting coupling, i.e., elements with subscripts 16 and 26 are zero. Elements with subscripts 45 are also zero for the stacking sequences considered. Although the 16 and 26 terms have been removed of the matrices,

the other terms of the B matrix were retained for generality. The present study involves the dynamic response of simply supported laminated composite circular cylindrical shells subjected to axisymmetric uniform radial pulse loads $p_z(t)$. All of the equations, the methods of solution and the analytical details are given by Plazaola [24].

3. MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND SHELL GEOMETRY

Shell structures made of graphite/epoxy and steel are analyzed. The geometrical and material parameters of the shell structures studied are given in Table 1. The laminate stacking sequences are as follows. For the GE00 case, $[0^\circ]_{40}$, for the GE90 case, $[90^\circ]_{40}$, for the GECP case, $[0_3^\circ/90_2^\circ]_{4s}$, and for the GECP1 case, (i.e. 100 plys) $[0_3^\circ/90_2^\circ]_{10s}$.

Material	Steel	Gr/Epoxy
E_{11} GPa	206.0	140.0
E_{22} GPa	206.0	15.6
E_{33} GPa	206.0	15.6
G_{12} GPa	79.2	6.0
G_{13} GPa	79.2	6.0
G_{23} GPa	79.2	6.0
ν_{12}	0.3	0.21
ν_{13}	0.3	0.21
ν_{23}	0.3	0.21
Density $k g/m^3$	7.85E+3	1.6E+3
Length m	1.2	1.2
Radius m	0.2	0.2
Ply thickness m	3.785E-3	1.27E-4

Table 1: Geometrical and material parameters

The thickness of the isotropic shell (steel) is chosen so that the bending stiffness of the isotropic shell equals the bending stiffness of the graphite/epoxy shell in the cross-ply configuration.

4. FREE VIBRATIONS

Details of the free vibration analysis are given by Plazaola [24]; only some of the results are presented herein. The classical shell theory (CST) and the refined shell theory (RST), the latter which includes the effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia, were used in this analysis. For the cases analyzed, the fundamental natural frequencies were identical up to the fifth significant figure for the steel (1S0), GE00, GE90, GECP, and GECP1 cases. The differences increase with increasing wave number m : however, up to wave numbers of 20, the maximum difference among the natural frequencies predicted by the CST theory and those predicted by the RST theory is of the order of 6%, because these are thin shells ($R/h=40$). This suggests that the CST theory may be used to carry out the forced vibration analysis shown herein without introducing substantial error.

According to [16], the effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia should be included for shells whose radius to thickness ratios are equal or less than twenty ($R/h \leq 20$). For completeness, the results predicted by the CST and RST theories show the natural frequencies can differ by 22% for large wave numbers for graphite/epoxy shells in a cross-ply configuration with a radius to thickness ratio of sixteen ($R/h = 16$), denoted as GECP1. This certainly supports the earlier results.

From [24] for both the CST and RST, the natural frequencies associated with each wave number differs significantly, the lower being the predominantly flexural mode, the higher being predominantly membrane action. For the RST, frequencies are found on order of magnitude above the lower two, which are predominantly rotational, i.e. primarily associated with the first thickness shear mode.

5. BLAST LOADS

The forced vibrations analysis involved investigating the response of the various composite shells to the five blast loads shown in Figure 2, taken from Dobyns [25], wherein analytical expressions for each are given. These expressions are also given Vinson and Sierakowski [4], and, of course, Plazaola [24]. It is assumed that the pulse load is acting axisymmetrically and uniformly over the shell surface. This is a good approximation for a pulse wave if the time the wave takes to travel a distance $2R$ is very small compared to the pulse duration (t_1).

Figure 2: Pulse shapes. (a) Sine. (b) Stepped. (c) Triangular. (d) Stepped triangular. (e) Exponential.

6. FORCED VIBRATIONS.

In order to determine the forced response, the method of eigenfunction expansions is used. The objective is to analyze not only the effects of the pulse features, such as pulse shape and pulse duration, but also the effects of the shell geometrical and material parameters.

The method of eigenfunction expansions or spectral method is used, wherein the dynamic response of the body can be represented as a superposition of its natural modes of vibration [26]. Because the eigenvalues are orthogonal, the displacement components are expressed as a linear combination of the natural modes. The orthogonality condition may be obtained by using Clebsch's theorem [26] combined with Hamilton's principle and Betti-Maxwell's reciprocal theorem. The procedure used by Plazaola [24] is based on the work of Krauss [26] and Dym [27], who presented an analysis for shells made of isotropic materials. In turn, each of the five blast loads of Figure 2 were studied in detail.

7 RESULTS

First, the effects of the pulse shape and pulse duration are investigated. Second, the effects of the laminate configuration and material are studied. Third, the effects of shell thickness are investigated, and a comparison of the results given by the CST theory and the RST theory is presented as well.

To study the effects of pulse characteristics, the GECP case was selected, using the CST theory. The response was obtained for three pulse shapes: the sine pulse, stepped pulse and the stepped triangular pulse.

To illustrate the dynamic response, the ratio W/W_{st} was selected, where W is the dynamic lateral deflection at the shell midlength ($x = L/2$), and W_{st} is the static deflection at the same location. The shell midlength is outside the bending boundary layer, $4[Rh (E_x/E_\theta)^{1/2}]^{1/2}$, for each composite shell studied. (See Reference 4) This ratio is also the same for the ratio of dynamic stresses to static stresses at that location.

It may be observed in Table 2, and shown in Figure 3, that the stepped pulse gives the greatest values of W/W_{st} . This holds true for the three selected values of the t_1/t_{1c} ratio.

Here, t_{1c} is the period of the fundamental shell frequency for that material architecture and geometry; t_1 is the pulse duration.

Pulse	t_1/t_{1c}		
	0.5	0.99	2.0
Sine	1.37	1.74	1.48
Stepped	1.89	1.97	1.98
Stepped Triangular	0.48	0.49	1.25

Table 2: Maximum W/W_{st} , GECP case.

The maximum W/W_{st} ratio is of the order of 2. It should be pointed out that the maximum response occurs while the pulse load is acting upon the shell surface, not after the pulse is completed. In addition, in a realistic environment, there will be material damping and perhaps air damping which will reduce the ratio in time. It may also be noticed in Table 2 that for the stepped pulse and stepped triangular pulse, the greatest

values of W/W_{st} occur for t_1/t_{1c} ratio of 2, whereas for the sine pulse the maximum occurs for $t_1/t_{1c} = 0.99$, and this ratio decreases for both narrower and wider pulses.

Figure 3: Dynamic response to a stepped pulse, $t_1/t_{1c} = 0.99$ GECP case

To investigate the effects of the laminate configuration and material, the ISO, GE00 and GE90 cases were studied. Since the stepped pulse cause the greatest values of W/W_{st} and since pulses whose t_1/t_{1c} ratios equal 2 also cause the greatest values of W/W_{st} , the response of these structures for such parameters is obtained. For each of the three cases, the maximum W/W_{st} is of the order of 2. However, the qualitative behavior of the motion is quite different. Plazaola [24] finds that the isotropic shell vibrates at a frequency approximately twice its fundamental frequency; The unidirectional 0° shell vibrates at a frequency that is 1.75 times its fundamental frequency and the unidirectional 90° shell vibrates at a frequency that is about 5.7 times its fundamental frequency. These shells, even though they have the same geometry, have different frequency spectra. Hence, the modes that are primarily excited differ for each shell as discussed by Dym [25] and many others.

The effects of the shell thickness are studied by considering a graphite/epoxy shell in a cross-ply configuration, denoted by GECP ($R/h = 40$) and GECP1 ($R/h = 16$). A comparison of the results, shown in [24] reveals that both shells qualitatively show the same behavior.

Regarding the results predicted by the CST theory and the RST theory, it may be pointed out that they are also quite similar. There is no significant difference in the dynamic response during the time interval in which the pulse load is acting on the shell surface. However, it may be noticed that for some loads, there are slight differences in both amplitude and phase, in the long term responses.

8: CONCLUSIONS

The dynamic response of laminated composite material circular cylindrical shells subjected to blast loads was studied, using Reissner-Naghdi shell theory, and including the effects of transverse shear deformation.

A free vibration analysis was carried out for four laminated composite material shells and for an isotropic shell as well. A comparison of the natural frequencies predicted by the classical shell theory and those predicted by the refined shell theory, indicates that, depending on the radius to thickness ratio, errors of the order of 20% or higher can occur by neglecting transverse shear effects.

Regarding the forced vibration analysis, the method of separation of variables and the method of eigenfunction expansions were used to determine the forced response. The solution to the dynamic problem for five blast pulse shapes was obtained. It was found that when the stepped pulse was used as the forcing function, the largest amplitudes of vibration were obtained. It was also found that the greatest values of the dynamic to static displacement ratio approach two, and correspond to pulse durations that are equal to one period or two periods of the vibration at the fundamental frequency, depending upon the material and the blast shape.

The effects of difference in thickness (R/h ratio) was also investigated. The results show no appreciable difference in the qualitative behavior of the response. Regarding the effects of including transverse shear deformation in the analysis, it was observed that even for the shell of $R/h = 16$, no substantial difference was obtained in the short term response ($t < t_1$), though slight differences, in amplitude and phase, were found in the long term response.

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